
Islamic Educational Thought in Building Students' Emotional Intelligence

Ika Kurnia Sofiani¹, Nabila², Neviani³, Selly Syalini⁴

¹Study Program of Pendidikan Agama Islam. STAIN BENGKALIS

^{2,3,4}Department of Tarbiyah Dan Keguruan. STAIN BENGKALIS

ABSTRACT: Islamic education plays an important role in developing the emotional intelligence of students. The concept of emotional intelligence in Islam is closely related to moral formation and the refinement of ethics. The Qur'an and Sunnah as the main sources of Islamic teachings offer a complete guide to building emotional intelligence which includes the ability to recognize one's emotions, manage emotions, motivate oneself, empathize, and foster good social relationships. Moral education in Islam aims to produce human beings who are not only intellectually intelligent, but also have high emotional and spiritual intelligence. The holistic approach in Islamic education integrates spiritual, intellectual, and physical formation so that learners grow into balanced and dignified individuals. Educational methods such as example, habituation, advice, and educative punishment are systematic efforts to shape the positive character and emotional intelligence of learners. This study explores the concept of emotional intelligence in the treasures of Islamic thought, analyzes the principles of Islamic education related to the development of emotional intelligence, and describes strategies and methods that can be implemented in the educational process to build emotional intelligence of students effectively and sustainably.

KEYWORDS: Islamic Education, Emotional Intelligence, Learners

INTRODUCTION

It must be realized that emotions are a domain of education. Unfortunately, today's students still have difficulty controlling their emotions. Islam not only regulates the relationship between humans and God but also the relationship between humans and humans and the relationship between humans and nature. In relationships between humans, clarity of consciousness is needed in behaving and acting so that humans can understand and comprehend each other, ultimately creating a harmonious atmosphere and all problems can be resolved (Nurjannah, 2016).

There is a stigma in society that intellectual ability is the most crucial aspect of education. As a result, there is a gap between the development of intellectual intelligence and emotional intelligence, which results in the emergence of negative behavior in students (Suntara, 2020). Currently, there are many cases of juvenile and student delinquency, including fights, suicide attempts due to failing national exams, depression due to being left by a boyfriend, promiscuous sexual behavior, robbery, use of illegal drugs, and other criminal acts (Ivan Riyadi, 2015).

Of course, educational problems in Indonesia are not only about students' academic or intellectual level. Education is not just a competition for students, which causes them to flock to number one, so it is not uncommon to hear news of cheating among the elite (Hujair A. H. Sanaky, 2008). Most teachers are fully responsible for the development of students at school by looking at the student's final results, so there is a lot of cheating and other bad attitudes that occur in morals, manners, and discipline, which should be the primary learning for students (Kamal, 2018).

In many cases, information about cognitive education that drives education makes all members of the educational system very interested in the student's level of knowledge. Specifically, students, parents, and teachers are interested in having students' intellectual abilities. Therefore, general knowledge is the most important factor in student development and prioritizes other students' knowledge. The student's cognitive abilities are the main focus of learning outcomes and often make educators pay less attention to students' other potential.

The Islamic view states that the potential possessed by students is something natural. If Islamic teachings adequately develop this potential, students will become loyal to Allah SWT. Humans created by Allah SWT have two essences, namely essential means and abilities or nature, which must be developed in practical life in this world through science. From a linguistic perspective, *fitrah* means creation, specific characteristics that characterize everything at the beginning of creation, and the inner characteristics of a person (from birth) (Pahurrozi, 2017). Among the potentials that need to be developed, the idea is that knowledge based on knowledge is too low for students to understand the importance of knowledge.

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Therefore, through good Islamic education, teachers should be able to guide students to develop their skills and qualities to the maximum through various learning methods (Harahap, 2017). Generally, Islamic religious education teachers continue to use traditional teaching approaches such as lectures and one-way teaching. Currently, learning methods in the world of education are changing and can help teachers in the learning process. Students' strengths cannot be developed in one classroom. Especially if teachers only focus on cognitive aspects and do not use various methods to test students' thinking abilities

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research uses a qualitative approach with literacy methods or library research (Tersiana, 2018). This method was chosen to explore the concepts and thoughts of Islamic education in building students' emotional intelligence through written sources. The primary and secondary sources of data. Primary sources include the Koran, Hadith, and classic works of Muslim thinkers on Islamic education and emotional intelligence. Secondary sources include books, journals, articles, and other literature that discuss related topics.

Data collection techniques were carried out through in-depth literature searches and exploration. The steps include identifying and searching for relevant literature sources, collecting and inventorying selected literature, reading, analyzing, and critically reviewing the literature contents, and recording and classifying important information according to the research topic. Data obtained from the literature will be analyzed using the content analysis method. The steps include; reducing data by sorting and summarizing important information, presenting data in systematic descriptions or narratives, drawing conclusions, and verifying research findings.

DISCUSSION

Understanding Emotional Intelligence According to an Islamic Perspective

Intelligence is the ability that enables individuals or systems to transform data, information, and knowledge into better knowledge, solve problems, and make effective decisions.

Artificial intelligence or Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a field of computer science which is devoted to solving cognitive problems, such as learning, creating, and recognizing images. Artificial intelligence has a variety of practical applications, such as intelligent document processing, AI-based APM tools, and strategies for monitoring and detecting application problems. AI rapidly evolves into artificial intelligence so that software can perform complex tasks like creating, making decisions, and learning independently. Artificial intelligence can benefit various industries by solving complex problems, monitoring and detecting problems before they occur, making applications run effectively, and resolving bottlenecks (htt1).

Intellectual intelligence refers to genetic and environmental factors that influence a person's level of intelligence. Genetic factors play a role in influencing a child's intelligence, but environmental factors can also influence genetic expression. The influence of environmental and genetic factors must be considered together in determining a person's intellectual intelligence. Human intelligence is not always related to academic achievement.

There are 9 types of human intelligence that we need to know, which are not always related to academic achievement. Human intelligence is not only related to academic achievement but is also related to the ability to learn and remember information, logical-mathematical intelligence, linguistic intelligence, emotional intelligence, spiritual intelligence, etc (htt2).

Meanwhile, emotions are a complex description of psychological and physiological states involving subjective feelings, thoughts, behavioral patterns, and biological changes in response to certain stimuli. Emotions are an essential aspect of human life that influences how individuals feel, think, and behave. Emotions can be positive, such as happiness, love, and gratitude, or negative, such as sadness, anger, and anxiety

Emotionally, humans are created with the ability to feel various complex feelings. Emotions are essential in helping individuals survive, adapt to the environment, and build meaningful social relationships. Emotions also play a role in the decision-making process, motivation, and creativity.

Emotions have interrelated components, namely:

1. Physiological Component: Physical changes occur in the body, such as increased heart rate, faster breathing, or cold sweat.
2. Behavioral Components: Facial expressions, body movements, and actions that reflect felt emotions.
3. Cognitive Component: Thoughts, judgments, and interpretations of situations that trigger emotions.
4. Subjective Component: Personally experienced feelings and emotional experiences.

Emotional intelligence is the ability to recognize, understand and manage emotions skillfully. Emotional intelligence allows individuals to control negative emotions, increase positive emotions, motivate themselves, empathize with others, and build healthy social relationships.

Emotional education from an early age is crucial to help individuals develop good emotional intelligence. Through emotional education, a person can learn how to express emotions appropriately, constructively manage emotions, and understand the feelings of others. Emotional education can also help individuals build resilience, increase self-confidence, and manage stress better.

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From an Islamic perspective, emotional intelligence has a broad and deep meaning. In Islamic scientific knowledge, emotional intelligence is closely related to moral development and refinement of character. The Qur'an and Hadith, as the main guidelines for Muslims, offer complete guidance on developing emotional intelligence that aligns with divine values. The definition of emotional intelligence in Islam is not only limited to the ability to recognize and manage one's emotions but also includes broader spiritual and moral aspects. In Islam, emotional intelligence is an integral part of the concepts of 'aql (reason) and qalb (conscience), which are the centres of control of human emotions, thoughts and behaviour.

Emotional intelligence in Islam is not just intellectual ability but also purity of heart and soul. A person who has good emotional intelligence is an individual who can control his passions, subdue anger, and always be patient, humble and forgiving. This is in line with the word of Allah SWT in the Qur'an, which commands humanity to always control their emotions, as in surah Ali Imran verse 134 (allah)

الَّذِينَ يَذُنُّونَ فِي السَّاءِ وَالضَّرَّاءِ وَالْفُظْمِ الْعَظِيمِ وَالْعِظْمِ الْعَظِيمِ عَنِ الزَّاسِ وَاللَّ

رْحَبِ الْمَحْشِيِّ (١٣٤)

They are those who donate in prosperity and adversity, control their anger, and pardon others. And Allah loves the good-doers. Emotional intelligence in Islam is closely related to morals and noble character. Rasulullah SAW was sent to perfect human morals, as he said: "Indeed I am sent to perfect noble morals." (HR. Ahmad). Morals that good is a manifestation of high emotional intelligence, where a person can control negative emotions, empathize with others, and behave in a commendable way (Murni, 2016).

The urgency of emotional intelligence in the life of a Muslim is very significant. Emotional intelligence helps individuals achieve happiness and peace of soul (sakinah). Someone with good emotional intelligence can overcome various challenges and trials more wisely without falling into destructive negative emotions.

Emotional intelligence is also essential in building harmonious and dignified social relationships. An emotionally intelligent Muslim can interact with others with compassion, respect differences, and avoid behaviour that hurts or degrades others. This aligns with Islamic teachings, emphasising the importance of maintaining friendship, helping each other and upholding peace. In the context of worship, emotional intelligence also plays an important role. A Muslim with good emotional intelligence can worship solemnly, sincerely, and without being overshadowed by negative emotions such as arrogance or riya.

Therefore, developing emotional intelligence is necessary for every Muslim who wants to achieve perfection of faith and morals. With the guidance of the Al-Qur'an and Sunnah and serious efforts to control emotions, a Muslim can achieve happiness in this world and, in the hereafter, become a human being whom Allah SWT loves and positively contributes to the environment and society.

Islamic Education Methods in Developing Emotional Intelligence

Islamic education offers various methods that can be implemented to develop students' emotional intelligence. These methods originate from the teachings of the Koran and Sunnah, and have been practiced by Muslim educators since the time of the Prophet SAW and his companions. These methods include, for example, habituation, advice and teaching, as well as educational punishment (Alifia Wahyuni Choirun Nisa, 2021).

First, an example (Uswatun Hashanah) is a fundamental educational method in Islam. The Prophet himself was the primary example for humanity in all things, including controlling emotions and noble morals. He is known for his patience, gentleness, and ability to manage emotions wisely. Rasulullah SAW always sets an example by educating his friends with commendable attitudes and behaviour. Therefore, an educator must be a good role model for his students in controlling emotions, empathy, and other noble morals. This example will be a real example for students in developing their emotional intelligence.

Second, the habituation method (ta'wid) effectively instils positive character and develops students' emotional intelligence (Zulfah, Z. dkk, , 2022). Habituation is done by repeating a good behaviour or habit consistently and continuously. For example, getting students used to saying hello, asking permission, thanking and apologizing. Habituation can also be done to control emotions, such as getting students used to being patient and not getting angry quickly when facing challenging situations. With regular and consistent habituation, students will get used to this positive behaviour and become part of their character.

Third, advice and teaching (mau'izah) is critical method in nurturing emotions and developing students' emotional intelligence (Muhammad Nur Hadi, 2019). In the Qur'an, Allah SWT often gives advice and teachings to humanity about how to manage emotions skillfully. For example, in Surah Ali Imran verse 134, Allah SWT praises people who can restrain their anger and forgive other people's mistakes. Educators can advise and teach students about the importance of controlling negative emotions, such as anger, envy, and envy, as well as developing positive emotions, such as compassion, empathy, and gratitude. This advice and teaching can be delivered through lectures, discussions, or inspirational stories that can raise students' awareness of the importance of emotional intelligence.

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Lastly, educational punishment (ta'dib) can be used as a method to correct student behavior that is deviant or related to poor emotional control (Maisyanah, dkk, 2020). However, the punishment referred to in Islam is not physical punishment or violence, but rather a punishment that is educational and guides students. Educate in a better direction. For example, they can warn students who misbehave or provide educational consequences such as writing self-reflections or doing social activities. This educational punishment aims to improve students' behavior and help them realize their mistakes and the impact of their actions so that they can learn to control their emotions better.

If implemented appropriately and continuously, these four methods will contribute greatly to developing students' emotional intelligence. The example of educators will provide tangible examples of how to manage emotions skillfully. Getting used to it will help instill consistent positive character and emotional control behavior. Advice and teaching will provide knowledge and understanding of the importance of emotional intelligence and ways to develop it. Meanwhile, educational punishment will help correct deviant behavior and build students' awareness of the importance of controlling emotions.

In practice, these methods must be carried out holistically and integrated in the school environment and at home. Educators and parents must work together to provide consistent examples, habituation, advice, and guidance to students. Apart from that, a conducive environment and a pleasant learning atmosphere are also essential to support the development of students' emotional intelligence.

By implementing these Islamic education methods optimally, it is hoped that students will grow into individuals who are not only intellectually intelligent but also have high emotional intelligence. They will be able to recognize and manage their emotions well, empathize with others, have strong motivation, and be able to build positive social relationships. Islamic education's primary goal is to form human beings with balanced spiritual, intellectual, and emotional intelligence.

Strategy and Implementation of Emotional Intelligence Education

Emotional intelligence education in Islam requires holistic and integrated strategies and implementation. This is in line with the principles of Islamic education, which prioritizes the comprehensive development of humans' spiritual, intellectual, and physical aspects. This strategy and implementation involves various parties, from educational institutions, teachers, parents, and the community (Susandi, 2021).

First, a holistic approach to Islamic education is crucial in developing students' emotional intelligence. This approach views emotional intelligence as a cognitive ability and involves spiritual, moral, and social aspects. Therefore, emotional intelligence education must be integrated with moral, faith, and social education. The curriculum and learning materials must be designed to emphasize academic aspects and teach divine values, noble morals, and social skills. Various learning methods, such as discussions, simulations, and field practice, can be used to facilitate the overall development of emotional intelligence.

Second, a conducive and supportive educational environment is crucial in developing students' emotional intelligence. This environment includes the school, home, and community environments. Schools must be safe, comfortable, and enjoyable places for students to learn and express themselves. A positive classroom atmosphere, harmonious relationships between teachers and students, and extracurricular activities that support the development of emotional intelligence must be prioritized. Parents must provide an environment full of love, attention, and a good example of controlling emotions at home. Meanwhile, in the community environment, it is necessary to create an atmosphere of mutual respect, tolerance and upholding good values.

Third, teachers, parents, and society are essential in implementing emotional intelligence education. Teachers have responsibilities excellent in providing role models, guidance, and appropriate teaching for Learners. Teachers must be skilled in recognizing and understanding students' emotions and be able to offer practical strategies to help them manage their feelings well. Teachers must also be patient, compassionate, and able to control their emotions well. On the other hand, parents significantly shape children's character and emotional intelligence from an early age. Parents must be good role models in controlling emotions, providing sufficient love, and supporting emotional intelligence education efforts in schools. Society also has a vital role in creating a conducive environment for developing emotional intelligence, for example, through social, religious, and cultural activities promoting positive values.

In its implementation, emotional intelligence education can be carried out through various strategies, such as:

1. Integrate emotional intelligence material and activities in the curriculum and learning processes at school, such as lessons about recognizing and managing emotions, empathy, self-motivation, and social skills.
2. Conduct training and workshops for teachers and parents on effectively educating and guiding children's emotional intelligence.
3. Organize extracurricular activities that support the development of emotional intelligence, such as social, artistic, sports, and religious activities.
4. Create a guidance and counseling program that explicitly addresses students' emotional intelligence issues.
5. Establish collaboration with related institutions or organizations such as psychologists, counselors, and character development institutions to support emotional intelligence education.

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6. Involving the community in activities that teach the values of kindness and controlling emotions, such as religious lectures, social service, or anti-violence campaigns.

With holistic and integrated strategies and implementation, it is hoped that students will grow into individuals who are not only intellectually intelligent but also have good emotional intelligence. They will be able to recognize and manage their emotions wisely, empathize with others, have strong motivation, and build positive social relationships. This is the primary goal of Islamic education, namely to form human beings who are balanced from a spiritual, intellectual, and emotional perspective.

Challenges and Solutions in Building Emotional Intelligence

In efforts to build emotional intelligence, primarily through education in the school and family environment, several challenges and problems must be faced. However, various preventive and curative efforts can be carried out to overcome these challenges by involving the participation of the community and society at large. Problems Faced in Emotional Intelligence Education are : (Hakim, 2015)

1. Lack of understanding of the importance of emotional intelligence: Many people still think that intellectual intelligence (IQ) is more important than emotional intelligence. It causes emotional intelligence education to receive less serious attention.
2. Lack of role models from the immediate environment: Students often do not get good role models in terms of controlling emotions from the closest environment, such as parents, teachers, or figures in society.
3. Inappropriate curriculum and learning methods: Curriculum and learning methods that are too oriented towards academic aspects can hinder the development of students' emotional intelligence.
4. Negative influence of media and technology: Excessive exposure to media and technology, especially content that contains violence or negative emotions, can hurt students' emotional intelligence.
5. Less conducive social environment: A social environment that is unsafe, full of conflict, or does not uphold good values can hinder the development of students' emotional intelligence.
6. Psychological factors and emotional disorders: Some students may experience psychological problems or emotional disorders that require special treatment.

Preventive and Curative Efforts to Overcome Challenges, namely: (Mubarok, 2019)

1. Increase awareness and understanding of the importance of emotional intelligence through outreach, seminars, and campaigns in various circles, both in schools, families, and communities.
2. Provide training and workshops for teachers, parents, and other stakeholders on effectively educating and guiding students' emotional intelligence.
3. Evaluate and improve the curriculum and learning methods to better holistically integrate aspects of emotional intelligence.
4. Implement clear rules and limits in the use of media and technology and provide education about the negative impacts of uneducated content
5. Creating a school, family and community environment that is safe, comfortable and upholds good values, such as tolerance, compassion and respect for others.
6. Provide guidance and counseling services for students who need special assistance in overcoming psychological problems or emotional disorders.

The Role of Communities in Supporting Emotional Intelligence Education

The role of the community and society is crucial to support the efforts made in the school and family environment.²⁰ Several roles that the community can carry out include:

1. Form groups or organizations that focus on developing emotional intelligence, such as character education groups, parenting communities, or youth development institutions.
2. Hold activities that support the development of emotional intelligence, such as emotional management training, empathy, and conflict resolution workshops, or social and religious activities that promote positive values.
3. Be a role model and an excellent example for society regarding emotional control, tolerance, and behavior that reflects good emotional intelligence.
4. Advocate and support policies that support emotional intelligence education at the school, family, and community levels.
7. Establish partnerships and collaboration with educational institutions, families, and other stakeholders to create a conducive environment for the development of emotional intelligence.
8. Providing support and facilities for activities to develop emotional intelligence, such as providing space for training, financial assistance, or other resources.

Comprehensive preventive and curative efforts and support from various parties, especially communities, and society, it is hoped that the challenges in building emotional intelligence can be overcome well. It will pave the way for the realization of a generation that is not only intellectually intelligent but also has good emotional intelligence so that it can face life's challenges more wisely and with dignity.²¹

CONCLUSION

Islamic education emphasizes developing pupils' emotional intelligence, which is a vital component of conscience and reason. It uses a variety of techniques, including education, counseling, and habituation, to control emotions, inculcate moral values, and discipline misbehaving behavior. A comprehensive approach encompassing educators, parents, the community, and educational institutions is needed to implement emotional intelligence education. But obstacles including ignorance, a lack of role models, unsuitable curricula, harmful media and technological influences, and psychological issues might impede its growth. Students can acquire balanced spiritual, intellectual, and emotional intelligence and make meaningful contributions to society, the environment, and themselves by utilizing Islamic education concepts and methodologies to the fullest extent possible.

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